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Diagnosis of Complex System in Mechanical with Multiple Failure Sources

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Abstract: This paper proposes a method to accurately locate the source of product quality drift in a flexible manufacturing system (FMS). Based on the relationship between fault sources, a fault propagation mechanism in the production process is proposed to explain fault propagation after production. Logic diagnostic models are used to reduce the search space for suspicious equipment in the production process; however, this does not help to accurately locate the faulty equipment. In the proposed method, we model this reduced search space as a Bayesian network, which uses historical data to calculate the conditional probability of each suspicious device. This method helps to make accurate decisions to locate the cause of product quality drift, whether it is one of the devices in the production process or the product itself.

Keywords: Fault Diagnosis, Complex Manufacturing System, Bayesian Network.

1. Introduction

One of the main challenges in the manufacturing field is to improve and optimize the quality of the production process and the activity of the equipment during the production operation. In order to improve product quality and reduce related costs, fault isolation, detection and diagnostic techniques have been developed. For fault diagnosis, many methods are proposed through diagnostic models, such as (Sampath et al., 1998; Deschamps & Zamai, 2007), which can locate the root cause of detected faults faster and more accurately. These methods are suitable for diagnosing faults from equipment and products. However, these methods cannot explain the effect of formula on product quality. In fact, due to the diversity of customer needs, production recipes are often changed, which may trigger an impact on product quality.

In addition, the production system includes hundreds of devices and is monitored by thousands of sensors. It is often difficult to identify the diagnostic model and corresponding variables.

Therefore, the artificial intelligence method is a very suitable technique for analyzing mass production information and describing the behavior of system components, as described by (Weber et al., 2012). These methods can be performed without knowing the underlying structure of the production system (Bouazizi et al., 2011). Among probabilistic methods, the Bayesian Network (BN) method is widely used to identify graphical structural models that describe the relationships between variables in a production system. Therefore, its conditional probability will be calculated to provide risk priority and support corrective maintenance decisions. Due to the complexity of today's manufacturing systems, the identification of this graphical structure is complex and needs to be performed by maintenance engineers (Bouazizi et al., 2011). Due to the introduction of new production technologies and maintenance management strategies, system elements such as products, recipes, equipment, maintenance schedules and human factors are constantly changing. Change is one factor that may trigger other factors. Therefore, we need to retrain the learning phase of the BN model to adapt to emerging situations in the production system. The amount of time and effort involved in calculations is very high, resulting in poor maintenance and additional costs.

Therefore, in this article, we propose: (I) a fault propagation mechanism to explain the relationship between different fault sources and their propagation in the production process; (ii) diagnostic methods using logical diagnostics (LD) models (De- (Schamps & Zamai, 2007) to reduce the search space for failed equipment in a given production stream and optimize the learning phase of subsequent of BN. Therefore, the joint probability and conditional probability of all error candidates will be calculated to support corrective maintenance decision making.

The characteristics of case study and the diagnosis objective are introduced in the next section. Section 3 introduces troubleshooting methods. In Section 4, we propose a fault model that can explain the impact and propagation of faults in the product flow. The LD model that causes the fault drift of suspicious equipment is described in Section 5. The proposed diagnostic model is described in Section 6. The conclusions and future outlook are discussed in Section 7.

2. Case Study & Diagnosis Objective

2.1 Case Study

The manufacturing process is constantly evolving to meet the growing demand for diversity. In addition, frequent changes in customer demand will lead to changes in corresponding products. As a result, flexible manufacturing systems (FMS) are widely used in complex and highly competitive manufacturing areas, such as the microelectronics and automotive industries. FMS is a complex

automated manufacturing system consisting of multiple production plants and connected by appropriate transportation systems. These production halls and transportation systems are controlled by control and automation systems. It usually has multiple products, production lines, formulations and human factors. In general, a complex system may have many production processes driven by control laws to meet the requirements of the control system. The structure of the production process describes the product type, product line and corresponding equipment in the operating part of the controlled system. Any changes made to one of the elements (e.g. product, equipment, recipe, and human) through control law will result in changes to existing processes.

Figure 1: A Flexible Manufacturing System

Therefore, the research in this article is based on a generally complex system in a dynamic production environment, which has the following characteristics: multiple products, production lines, and recipes, as shown in Figure 1. In addition, the failure can come from different sources such equipment, products and recipes.

2.2 Diagnosis Objective

In complex engineering applications, a system can consist of many components and subsystems. The way in which these elements interact affects the way faults propagate within and across subsystem boundaries (Hine, 2005). In this article, we believe that the cause of the failure may belong to the product, equipment and formula. To monitor the execution of system components, layered and modular controls are often used (Jones & Saleh, 1990). In this case, the automated

manufacturing system organized by the Computer Integrated Manufacturing (CIM) architecture includes: a controlled system, a product process, and a control system, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CIM Architecture of an Automated Production System

The controlled system consists of actuators and sensors. Sensors monitor the execution of actuators and product flows. Therefore, the actuators and sensors are controlled by a local control module. The collection of these elements is called the function chain (FC) (Henry et al., 2005). The FC receives requirements from the coordination level of the control system and executes them according to the product requirements. When the FC cannot execute the requirements correctly, it indicates a failure. Actually, there are many positions of actuators or products that cannot be observed by sensors. Therefore, when a failure occurs, it cannot be observed that it may spread from one FC to another FC through the production line. Therefore, it is called fault propagation. As a result, this fault propagation not only leads to potential product failures, but also affects other system components. Therefore, new failures may be created. Therefore, when a fault is detected by metering, the root cause may come from one or a part of the system elements. In short, the diagnostic goal is to accurately and quickly locate the possible root cause of the fault to support

the maintenance operator to save the recovery time of the production system (for restoring normal conditions).

3. Literature Review of Diagnosis Methods

Diagnostic techniques based on fault propagation analysis component dependencies include propagation diagrams (AbdelWahed and Karsai, 2006) and chronic tense (Strasser & Sheppard, 2011). These methods are based on historical production data to locate components that may be the origin of the detected fault. However, these methods do not analyze the behavior of the functional Chain (FC), so they cannot explain the consequences between FC elements and between different of FC. Moreover, these methods cannot reduce the size of the model. Due to the periodic operation of the control system, a large amount of information from the production system raises the problem of combinatorial explosion. Therefore, we are particularly interested in the logic diagnostic model proposed in (Deschamps & Zamai, 2007). In this model, a diagnostic function is proposed to characterize the historical information of the controlled system to search for suspicious potential fault sources in real time. Therefore, the model provides a set of possible origins in the form of a directed graph, and its size is reduced by using the observations of the controlled system. This is suitable for diagnosing faults in production equipment and products. However, this method cannot explain the effect of the formula on product quality and its relationship with other system elements. In fact, any change in the production formula can trigger product quality drift. In addition, the model does not show the suspicious level of each possible source candidate in the diagnostic results. It is difficult to determine the order of maintenance in complex systems. Therefore, the method will be extended to optimize corrective maintenance activities.

Regarding the risk priority of potential failure candidates, probabilistic methods are widely used, such as neural networks (Khomfoi & Tolbert, 2007) and Bayesian networks (Weber et al., 2012). These methods can calculate probability values from large databases and can calculate related variables from production systems. These probability values allow the suspicious level (high or low) to be evaluated to support the decision of the maintenance strategy. In particular, the BN model has the advantage that, as described (Weber et al., 2012), it can be applied to manufacturing. (Bouazizi et al., 2011) introduced a BN-based method to diagnose in multivariable systems. The compression level of the feedback information is proposed in (Duong et al., 2013) to provide a probability value that shows the state of the compression performed by the device for incorrect execution. When the database is available, these methods are useful tools for calibration

maintenance. However, it must be expanded due to the following issues. As described by Duong et al. (2013), the structure of the aggregation level model of information feedback is static with seven parameters. In the case of a flexible manufacturing system with a variety of products, production lines, formulations, and human factors, the production situation usually changes as we introduced in Section 2. Therefore, the parameter set device level that may affect condensation is dynamic. In addition, the BN model must be updated based on information on new production conditions. In practice, learning methods are commonly used to model BN when information from the database is available (as described by Neal and Hinton, 1998). In the learning method, the graph structure and probability rules are estimated from the observed data. Many studies in (Bouazizi et al., 2011; Neal & Hinton, 1998) indicate that these learning methods remain complex in determining variables because they rely heavily on expert opinion. The computational learning workload is still significant (Neal & Hinton, 1998). This wastes too much time and is not suitable for real-time structure recognition because it depends on the utilization of the database. In fact, the production environment is under increasing pressure from fierce competition. It shows that it is important to find the root cause of the failure and the time for the process to recover (to bring the process back to normal). These challenges drive research into the application of BN models to real-time fault diagnosis and corrective maintenance optimization.

This paper proposes a diagnostic model that can locate real-time faults and root causes in equipment, products, and recipes, so as to dynamically calculate the conditional probability between faults and their possible causes. This is based on a logic diagnostic model and a BN model. Therefore, the diagnostic mechanism is based on four main steps: (i) The LD model provides a set of possible root causes of failure. The relationship of members in this set is used to build the graph structure, and (ii) we use this structure for the BN model. The idea is to simplify the identification of variables in the BN learning phase, (iii) the historical information of the production system is used to estimate the probability rules of the BN model learning phase, and (iv) the conditional probability of the nodes is calculated in the structural model. These probability values allow the risk priority of each possible source of failure to be evaluated. However, the structure of the BN model largely depends on the causality between members in the set of possible origins, while the LD model only describes the propagation of equipment failures and corresponding information (products and recipes), without explaining their cause and effect relationship. Therefore, we

analyze these relationships, so the failure propagation mechanism in the production process will be proposed in the next section.

4. Failure Propagation Mechanism

4.1 Relationships Between Equipment, Recipes & Product Quality

The diagnostic goal of this article is to accurately and quickly locate the root cause of failures that may originate from equipment, products and formulations. In fact, the relationship between fault sources only affects product quality. Therefore, this section will analyze these causal relationships. Product quality depends on the state of the equipment as described in (Sampath et al., 1998). However, this effect will change when considering formula elements. Therefore, we propose a definition of the formula and then analyze its impact on the quality of equipment and products. The concept of recipes is widely used in the control of flexible manufacturing systems. The representation of the production process is based on the concept of controlled operations with basic and control recipes developed by all major suppliers of process control systems through rigorous process R & D, which are used in batch processing plants Automation, as described in (Mergen, 1990). The basic recipe is device independent, which describes the production process for a given technology. It is designed to make products whose quality depends on the basic formula. The equipment executes the requirements of the basic recipe by controlling the recipe. The transition to control recipes includes basic recipes, production plans, multipurpose plant descriptions and executable control recipes (Genrich et al., 1994), as shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: The Process to Create a Control Recipe

Generally, control recipes are created based on the characteristics of the system and tested before they are applied to an actual system (Mergen, 1990). Therefore, the control recipe does not trigger equipment failure. However, due to different physical characteristics, different devices perform the same control recipe and provide different product quality. In addition, equipment performance may be beneficial for one formulation but poor quality for other formulations. Therefore, as shown in Figure 4, there is a causal relationship between equipment, formula and product quality. This means that product quality drift can come from part or part of a physical equipment failure and control recipe.

Figure 4: The Relationship Between Different Failure Sources

During production, failure may propagate from one device to another through the production flow. Therefore, these causal relationships also spread with production flows. This issue is covered in the next section.

4.2 Failure Propagation Mechanism

Failures that occur on the device may come from physical failures of itself and / or the input product. As a result, faults occurring on the equipment and corresponding control methods may be propagated to the finished product. All in all, there is a causal relationship between product quality and the complete set of equipment and formulations. These relationships continue to propagate across the product flow, so they lead to fault propagation during production, as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Failure Propagation in a Production Process

Figure 5 illustrates that the source of failure for production j may come from equipment j and control recipe j. Therefore, the cause of the failure on device j may be product i and product k to device i of device j, control recipe i, Equipment k, and control recipe k. As a result, faults are propagated in the product. Therefore, after using the LD model to propagate faults on the product flow, we locate the possible fault sources of the detected faults. The principle of the LD model will be introduced in the next section.

5. Logical Diagnosis Model

(Deschamps & Zamai, 2007) proposed a logic diagnostic model as part of dealing with fault diffusion through products in complex production processes. In this model, a diagnostic function is proposed to characterize historical information from a controlled system when locating the probable cause of a detected fault. The diagnostic function is mainly reflected in three aspects:

- First, the necessary information is collected from the coordination level for fault diagnosis through operation and maintenance models (Henry et al., 2005). The operation model contains information on the function chain (equipment, sensors, and local control modules), (prerequisites) conditions, (prerequisites) constraints, and operations, as shown in Figure 6. The diagnostic model describes the graphical structure of the production process consisting of system components (see illustrated in Figure 7) and their relationships are as following product flows (the arrows in Figure 7)

Operation O_i		
Functional chain ec_j	Service Se_i	
During Du_i		
Evolution of function chain ec_i		
Effect	Pre-condition	Pre-contrain
	$Pcd(ec_j)$	$Pct(ec_j)$
↓ IC(EfT(ec_j))	Condition	Contrain
Transient effect EfT (ec_j)	$Cd(ec_j)$	$Ct(ec_j)$
↓ IC(EfF(ec_j))		
Final effect EfF(ec_j)		
Premier Evolution of flow of product $ea_{i,1}$		
Effet	Pre-condition	Pre-contrain
	$Pcd(ea_{i,1})$	$Pct(ea_{i,1})$
↓ IC(EfT($ea_{i,1}$))	Condition	Contrain
Transient effect EfT ($ea_{i,1}$)	$Cd(ea_{i,1})$	$Ct(ea_{i,1})$
↓ IC(EfF($ea_{i,1}$))		
Final effect EfF($ea_{i,1}$)		

Figure 6: Operation Model

- Second, a mechanism for simplifying this model is developed by using controlled system observations. After performing operations in this model, if the information provided by these two elements is inconsistent, the controlled system sends an incorrect execution report to the coordination level. If the coordination level does not receive an erroneous execution report from these functional links, it can be concluded that the corresponding element is reliable. These reliable elements (black nodes in Figure 7) will be removed from the model, while suspicious elements (white nodes in Figure 7) will remain.
- Finally, a mechanism based on the fault propagation method (the dashed arrow ` in Figure 7) defines a mechanism that allows us to search for possible origins and consequences for

errors when the model receives an error execution report from a functional module. The chain diagram is shown in Figure 7.

Indeed, this logic diagnostic model provides a simplified structural model and a set of suspicious operations that are logically related to the faulty execution. These suspected operations are considered as possible origins $\{O_1; \dots; O_i; \dots; O_n\}$ against detected fault. The simplified model describes the logical connections between possible sources of failure. Therefore, these logical links are considered causal in terms of fault propagation. The simplified model is in the form of a directed graph, where nodes represent suspicious operations, and arcs represent fault propagation paths that propagate through product flows.

For fault diagnosis with equipment failure, products and control recipes, we consider that an operation O_i contains information of the equipment E_i , as the corresponding control recipe R_i and the product P_i associated with the equipment E_i as conditions for operating O_i . The final effect of O_i . Therefore, we obtained a set of possible failed devices $\{E_1; \dots; E_i; \dots; E_n\}$, a set of control recipes $\{R_1; \dots; R_i; \dots; R_n\}$ and a set of products $\{P_1; \dots; P_i; \dots; P_n\}$. For example, a fault propagates from operation O_i to operation $O_i + 1$. The LD model can locate suspicious operations and the

corresponding equipment, products and recipes. However, it does not describe the relationships within the operation. For this reason, we propose a failure propagation mechanism in a complex process to explain their causes, as described in Section 4. Therefore, the directed graph describes the failure propagation from operation O_i to operation O_{i+1} . The causality in these operations is shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8: Possible Fault Origins Inside Operations

Moreover, in order to evaluate the risk priority of each candidate, the information provided by the directed graph and the complete set of equipment, products and recipes will be used for the structural identification of the BN model. Therefore, the conditional probability is calculated by a diagnostic model, which is described in the next section.

6. Diagnosis Model

6.1 Model Description

The proposed model consists of a logic diagnostic model and a BN model, as shown in Figure 9. In this model, we use the results given by the logic diagnostic model introduced in Section 5 for

dynamic structural identification of BN. Probability values are then calculated by the BN model to support the decision to perform corrective maintenance.

Figure 9: Diagnosis Model

The diagnostic model is based on a control system and dynamic recognition (Henry et al., 2005; Deschamps & Zamai, 2007). Reactive loops are characterized by the collaboration of multiple supervisory, surveillance, and control (SM & C) functions, such as detection, diagnosis, prognosis, decision making, and automatic control (Zamai et al., 1997). The coordination level of the control system has the ability to manage a set of function chains and corresponding information. It requires and remembers the information in the production database. It also provides diagnostic information. Our method includes: (i) searching for possible root causes of failures detected during the past evolution of operating components within the controlled system, and (ii) calculating probability values that show suspicious levels for candidate objects. The implementation of the diagnostic model is explained as follows:

- The model is generated at the coordination level. Therefore, it can send commands in real time and receive real-time reports of all system components. This level of coordination also provides the necessary information for logical diagnostics.
- Once a fault is detected through metrology, a logical diagnostic model will define a set of possible origins and their correlations.

- This set of possible origins and corresponding information is sent to the BN model. Therefore, the graphical structure of the failure mode is determined to support structure recognition in the learning phase of the BN model.
- After the graphical structure of the BN model is established, the conditional probability associated with all nodes in the network is calculated based on the historical information in the production database. The results of all calculations are stored in a production database to support decision making for corrective maintenance.

6.2 The Execution of Diagnosis Model

When a fault is detected by metering, the diagnostic model will manage its execution and will require the diagnostic results of the logical diagnostic model and the BN model. The logic diagnostic model provides a set of possible faulty devices $\{E_1; \dots; E_i; \dots; E_n\}$, and the corresponding control recipe $\{R_1; \dots; R_i; \dots; R_n\}$ and product set $\{P_1; \dots; P_i; \dots; P_n\}$, as described in Section 5. They are sent to the BN through the coordination level and used to build the BN model. Conditional probability is calculated according to the main theory proposed in (Manfredotti, 2009). The establishment and execution of the BN model are as follows:

- First, the graphical structure of the BN model is converted from the set of equipment, control recipes, and products that may be faulty given by the logical diagnostic model. Each member of these sets is considered a node in the BN model. The device $E_{i'}$; ($i' = 1 \dots n$; $i' \neq i$) is the parent of E_i if it is in front of node E_i and has a direct logical relationship with E_i after the product flow in the directed graph. The product $P_{i'}$ corresponding to $E_{i'}$ is placed between $E_{i'}$ and E_i , and the control formula for $E_{i'}$ is regarded as the parent of $P_{i'}$.

Therefore, we obtained the graphical structure of the BN model. Each node in the structure can be the parent of a child node or a child of another parent node. For example, the parents of the detected failed node are E_i and R_i . So, E_j has a group of parents those are $\{P_{i-1}^1, \dots, P_{i-1}^k, O_{i-1}^N\}$, with $K_j = 1 \dots N$. Apart from, Parents of each node P_{i-1}^k are E_{i-1}^k and R_{i-1}^k . In this case, the BN model has a hierarchical structure as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Graphical Structure of BN Model

Second, each node in the BN model is assigned $N_j, j=1 \dots n$ to facilitate the computation. Each node N_j has a set of parents as $\{N_j^1, \dots, N_j^{K_j}, \dots, N_j^{n_j}\}$, with $K_j=1 \dots n_j$. Therefore, the learning phase of the BN model is performed to calculate the probability $P(N_j | \text{Product})$ for each node N_j following the product, the second is the conditional probability between the child node and its parent node based on the historical information of the production database. We consider that each member of the fault origin set has two states $\{1, 0\}$. Therefore, the conditional probability on each node N_j with ($j=1 \dots n$) and its parents are defined as a matrix $P(N_j | N_j^1, \dots, N_j^{n_j})$ as the next equation:

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P(N_j = 1 | N_j^1 = 1, \dots, N_j^{k_j} = 1, \dots, N_j^{n_j} = 1) \\
 &P(N_j = 1 | N_j^1 = 0, \dots, N_j^{k_j} = 0, \dots, N_j^{n_j} = 0) \\
 &P(N_j = 0 | N_j^1 = 1, \dots, N_j^{k_j} = 1, \dots, N_j^{n_j} = 1) \\
 &P(N_j = 0 | N_j^1 = 0, \dots, N_j^{k_j} = 0, \dots, N_j^{n_j} = 0)
 \end{aligned}$$

(1)

In this article, in order to calculate the conditional probability, when we need to extract a certain subset of variables or the distribution of a single variable, we need to marginalize or sum the variables as mentioned in (Manfredotti, 2009), focus on variables other than variables. The marginalization rules for any variable X and Y are given by:

$$P(X) \sum_y P(X, y); y \in Y \quad (2)$$

The distribution on X can be obtained by summing all other variables in any joint distribution containing X. We can use conditional probability instead of joint probability calculate the probability on X as shown below

Equation (3):

$$P(X) \sum_y P(X|y).P(y); \in Y \quad (3)$$

Finally, the model calculates the conditional probability P (N_j | fault, product) on node N_j based on the product, which is given by the detected fault (j = 1...n), as shown in the following equation:

$$P(N_j | fault, Product) = \prod_{i=1}^n \sum_{N_i} P(N_j).P(N_i | N_j).$$

$$P(fault | N_1, \dots, N_i, \dots, N_n, Product) \quad (4)$$

With $i=1 \dots n, \quad i \neq j$. They are used to support maintenance decisions.

The above sections show that when a failure is detected, the set of possible origins is determined dynamically. Therefore, when data is available, the diagnostic model will calculate the corresponding conditional probability. This set of possible root causes and these probability values are sent through the coordination level and stored in the production database.

6.3 Discussion

The advantages of the proposed model are: firstly, locate the possible fault origin set in real time, secondly reduce the space of the defect set by assessing the suspicious level, and finally reduce the workload for structural identification of the BN model. In the proposed model, the logical diagnostic model significantly reduces the possible root causes. Next, this is used to simplify the structural identification of the BN model. Therefore, the graphical structure received by the BN model contains only elements as possible sources of detected faults. Other elements unrelated to the detected fault will be deleted. Therefore, it does not need to calculate all probabilities for all elements in the production system.

In addition, the probability value calculated by the BN model helps to continue to reduce the set of possible origins through risk priority to save the recovery time of the production system. This also means that the combination of a deterministic method (logical diagnosis) and a probabilistic method (Bayesian network) helps us locate the device more accurately and faster as the root cause of a detected fault. Therefore, the model can be used for fault diagnosis in complex automated production systems with large amounts of production information.

7. Conclusion

This article proposes a failure propagation mechanism to describe the impact of recipes on equipment and product quality, and to explain the fault propagation mechanism during production. Therefore, the proposed diagnostic model can dynamically generate the structure and correlation probability of BN. We use logical diagnostic models to significantly reduce the search space for suspicious devices in a given production flow. As shown in the figure, this reduced set of possible sources provides a causal relationship to simplify the identification of the fault model during the BN learning phase. In addition, the BN model calculates related probabilities to assess the suspiciousness of each member in the set of possible fault sources. Therefore, in the case of a complex manufacturing system featuring multiple products, production lines, and recipes, the model is suitable for dynamically locating the root cause and calculating the workload with less time and less conditional probability values. As a result, diagnostic results can support the decision to make corrective maintenance activities.

In future work, we are interested in applying the proposed diagnostic method to a production system to evaluate the performance of the proposed method. Therefore, corresponding algorithms need to be developed to adapt to real-time manufacturing systems. In addition, we will improve failure diagnosis in general manufacturing systems with multiple fault sources.

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Dedication

Not mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

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